

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF INCREASING YOUTH SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN FORMING CIVIL SOCIETY

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Abstract: Nowadays, the democratic principles of the life of advanced countries are evaluated by the fact that they raise the human value to such a high level. At this point, the essence of fundamental changes and reforms taking place in our country comes from this principle. In the implementation of this principle, the formation of a new outlook and healthy thinking based on the harmony of national and universal values is of great importance. It should be emphasized that the processes of democratic reforms implemented in the field of education in our society lead to the prioritization of universal values, despite the diversity of citizens' national-spiritual and educational potential and social activities.

In this article, the importance of increasing the social activity of young people in the formation of civil society is scientifically researched.

Key words: civil society, social activity, young people, mature generation, qualities of social activity, intellectual potential.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ МОЛОДЕЖИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ГРАЖДАНСКОГО ОБЩЕСТВА

Аннотация: В наши дни демократические принципы жизни передовых стран оцениваются тем, что они поднимают человеческую ценность на такой высокий уровень. На данный момент суть коренных изменений и реформ, происходящих в нашей стране, исходит из этого принципа. В реализации этого принципа большое значение имеет формирование нового мировоззрения и здорового мышления, основанного на гармонии национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей. Следует подчеркнуть, что процессы демократических реформ, реализуемых в сфере образования в нашем обществе, ведут к приоритету общечеловеческих ценностей, несмотря на многообразие национально-духовного и воспитательного потенциала и общественной активности граждан.

В данной статье научно исследуется значение повышения социальной активности молодежи в формировании гражданского общества.

Ключевые слова: гражданское общество, социальная активность, молодежь, зрелое поколение, качества социальной активности, интеллектуальный потенциал.

INTRODUCTION

At present, more than 60 percent of the population of Uzbekistan are young people. That is why, at the heart of all the positive changes being implemented in our country, care is taken for a young generation that is well-rounded - physically healthy, mentally mature, who has acquired not only a lot of knowledge, professions that are in high demand nowadays, but also is capable of independent and creative thinking, and has a high intellectual potential. It is natural that the priority goal is to do.

The comprehensive measures taken to create all the favorable conditions for the comprehensive development of the young generation growing up in the country are a characteristic of our people and have become an integral part of our national nature. As our country's President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev noted: "It is known that education of the young generation has always been important and relevant. But in the 21st century we live in, this issue is becoming a matter of life and death. "The more perfect the education, the happier the people," say the sages.

In order for education to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to appear in this matter"[1].

In every family, in every neighborhood, first of all, it has been an important issue to ensure the health of young people, to give them a good education, and at the same time, to raise them to be worthy persons with high spiritual and moral qualities. In the years of independence, these tasks were raised to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan, which allowed to achieve high achievements in all areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the context of the realization of the national identity of young people, it is important to study and theoretically research their social interests, which are as follows:

- from the point of view of the diversity of opinions, social interests are analyzed through existing concepts and expressed in the form of views typical of modern conditions;
- the role and importance of social interests in the development of society is studied in a harmonious way with political and economic interests in modern political processes;
- sociologically analyzes the nature, content and role of social interests in the development of society;
- influences the socio-political, economic and spiritual factors in the society on social interests;
- in the current period, he theoretically studies the features of the development of the processes of social development, the style of ethnic interests, national and universal content.

"Youth is a period of searching for a divine ideal, forming goals and a life position, choosing a profession, and preparing for family life. For young men and women who are entering life, their activities are not only socially useful, but also very important because this activity corresponds to their personal goals, aspirations, and helps them realize their life plans as much as possible"[2].

In the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, there is a need to improve the institutional system of increasing the social activity of young people. Increasing the social activity of young people is an organizational-pedagogical process aimed at a specific goal, in which the qualities of social activity formed in young people are improved and enriched.

RESULTS

In a democratic society, social activism is a means of self-realization of citizens. An important condition for the success of the democratic reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is to rely on the social activity of our people, every citizen.

It is necessary to recognize this as an objective law of universal development. After all, we have a long and difficult road ahead of us. If we all stick together, study tirelessly, do our work perfectly and efficiently, acquire modern knowledge, and move forward relentlessly, our lives and society will definitely change. For this, of course, it is necessary to increase social activity and initiative among young people.

Today, the concept of "social activity" is understood in a broad sense, that is, a quality that reflects the level of socialization of a person, the depth of acceptance of social interests, and in a narrow sense, his connections with a certain social unit.

The goals, methods and means of activity, their content are determined by the values and social norms accepted in this society. And, of course, the activity should be consistent and step-by-step - operationally specific, functionally effective. The activity should be not only holistic,

goal-oriented, motivational, but also clearly meaningful in a certain social environment, emotionally comfortable, understood, and socially meaningful.

The main components of the activity are: "the motive, the main goal, the analysis of the existing situation, reference to past experience, the selection of specific goals in the implementation of operations, achieving results, comparing the obtained result with the desired one." Therefore, one of the urgent tasks of today is to encourage and guide all layers of society, especially young people, to successful and positive activities. Therefore, teaching young people to be active from childhood is the basis for achieving success in the future. Therefore, increasing the social activity of students in the pedagogical process is the scientific-pedagogical basis of building a democratic and legal society.

As mentioned above, social activity is a higher manifestation of a certain activity of a person in society, and this process includes social interest, social experience, social maturity and social portrait in a person.

The reforms being carried out in our country today change the intellectual potential of our people in all areas with a new worldview and require increasing the social activity of students. In this process, the spiritual memory of our people is being restored, the social activity of young people is keeping pace with the times and is being manifested in various aspects of spiritual life. In such conditions, it is very important to support the initiative and enthusiasm, patience and perseverance, enthusiasm and creativity of students for social activity. Moral visions, which have been settled and formed for many years in our country, restoration of spiritual skills in the minds of young people and their development based on the requirements of the new era have become a big social problem. In this way, a number of decisions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev became important. In our country, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 14, 2016 "On State Policy Regarding Youth", March 14, 2017 "On Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Secondary Special Vocational Education Institutions", July 18, 2017 "On Improving the Activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" on comprehensive measures" dated July 28, 2017 "On increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level" dated September 13, 2017 "Development of the system of publication and distribution of book products, increasing book reading and reading culture and decisions on comprehensive promotion measures and July 5, 2017 "On improving the efficiency of the state youth policy and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan", January 25, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of general secondary, secondary special and vocational education", 2018 The decrees of June 27, 2018 on the State program "Youth are our future" and the adoption of the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 23, 2018 "On approving the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism" served to turn our youth into a socially active layer.

DISCUSSION

Civil society directly indicates that people, young people are developing a new social attitude to life, their profession and occupations, and new changes are taking place in their social activity. If young people do not have social activity in their labor activity, type and direction of training, if there is no attitude to life based on the laws of thinking, hope, efficiency and grateful labor process will not occur in their actions. All events and measures aimed at reforming the social spheres of the country are aimed at beautifying the life and future of our people and youth, moral upliftment, bringing to adulthood individuals with high moral thinking, worldview and

consciousness. That is why the social activity of young people started to be formed on the basis of high human feelings, getting acquainted with the world experience. Therefore, it was put on the agenda as an important social task to increase the development of society and the social activity of the young generation, to save their worldview, spirituality, and moral thinking from the influence of destructive ideas.

The strategy of actions for the renewal and development of Uzbekistan became the theoretical basis for all economic, social, ideological processes, reforms and led to the increase of social activity of young people, renewal and development.

In the process of social development, the spiritual world, moral standards, legal culture, philosophical heritage, political mentality and social activity integrated into rich traditions of each nation have a special place. These, in turn, encourage young people to have their own "I" in society, to preserve the historicity and authenticity of the social environment. It is the goal of the legal democratic and civil society to educate young people who are fully developed and have a high moral culture in our country.

It is also necessary to pay attention to the following aspects in order to increase the social activity of young people and educate them in the spirit of initiative and hard work:

1. Ensuring the integration of state bodies, neighborhood institutes and schools with the process of increasing the social activity of young people, directing the worldview of young people towards social life, connecting them with a sense of confidence in the future with national pride, national pride, love for the Motherland, loyalty to the country, respect for the country;

2. Forming the skills of young people to effectively use all the opportunities created by the state, to decide their social activity based on the sense of goodness and sophistication;

3. To form a worldview aimed at respecting all people on earth regardless of their nationality, race, religion, language, gender, social origin, position, and carrying out joint social activities in young people;

4. Every parent should enrich the pure feeling in the heart of the newly born baby with ideals of social thinking and culture, and instill in him the feeling of building a prosperous life and a beautiful life in the national spirit. All these aspects show the harmony, harmony and unity of the social and political work carried out in our social life with work.

Creating conditions for increasing social activity of young people can form a civil society without any obstacles. In the current situation, it is necessary to create such conditions for young people, in which it is necessary to increase their political and legal activity and the number of youth public organizations. These processes serve as the basis for the formation of external conditions in our country's movement towards civil society.

Today, one of the most urgent tasks is to develop creative, free thinking ability, independent learning needs and skills in our youth. When talking with foreigners who have experience of communicating with young people from Uzbekistan, they emphasize that our young people are ambitious, hardworking, have extensive knowledge in all fields, and that it would be better if they pay more attention to the formation of their creative, free thinking, ability to apply knowledge in practice, independent learning needs and skills. they admit. Therefore, this issue is always reflected in all strategies aimed at ensuring the long-term development of countries.

A new approach to education, innovative educational technologies that need to be introduced at the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, should be based on the activity of more learners, should be aimed at forming their independent learning needs and skills. It is necessary for the teacher to move from the role of knowledge transferer to the role of organizer of the active

learning process of students, psychologically and pedagogically rationally supporting and developing their existing knowledge, free thinking, creativity, and innovation needs.

Improvement of the education system and its quality, implementation of step-by-step consistent development in all areas of education is the foundation laid for the future. We all know that the result of the development of the educational system is an important factor underlying the socio-economic well-being of Uzbekistan. If we pay attention to the developed countries, their achievements and development are related only and only to the factor of high knowledge, aspiration and free activity and thinking created for young people.

The information society is putting modern demands on us to increase the social activity of our youth. This, in turn, brings the creation of modern science programs and textbooks to the current level, with our mature scientists and specialists thoroughly studying the best practices and technologies of foreign countries and adapting them to our national mentality.

Issues related to youth are closely related to education, morals, culture, health care, social relations, politics, law, religion, organization of free time, family, work, sports. Therefore, in the scientific literature, these problems related to young people are studied both in the social system and as a specific social group in a differential way. Today, the determination and finding of their place in society by young people is taking place in the era of the fading of old views, values and the formation of new social relations. That is why there are cases of aggression, indifference, extremist moods and confusion among young people. Young people are subjects of social relations. Because of this, high social activity and responsibility are demanded from them today.

The social activity of young people serves as a unique guide for the correct understanding of their role and task in life and its realization. It can be either fruitful for the society or alien to the limited, unstable, independence that leads to the passivity of the individual. According to psychologists, "the need to express oneself, to be active, to realize oneself arises during youth, the choice of the field of self-realization and its methods occurs, first of all, in the youth years." It is a requirement of life to learn how young people can control themselves, analyze their life strategy, get used to serious relationships and participate in one or another social trends that shape a certain life space in order to express life perspectives in public life. This includes the following key indicators:

- level of patriotism and loyalty to the Motherland;
- problems that concern young people;
- feeling social;
- priority life values and plans;
- level of social maturity.

Today, scientists in increasing the social activity of young people, analyzing and researching problems related to young people, who have their own psychological characteristics and characteristics, define their social position in society based on the social, economic, cultural and spiritual development of this society, and treat them as a separate demographic group. They are trying. Therefore, it is important to develop a new approach to the pedagogical and psychological aspects of increasing youth activity.

The social activity of young people, the choice of their personal place in life is manifested in various spheres of human life and practice, and is carried out through education, re-examining and incorporating the experience of the older generation. Social norms, values and wealth are the main socio-psychological managers and indicators of this process. It is these that determine the

mental and practical activity of young people, the specifics of their problems, their interests and expected results, and the characteristics of self-management and management.

In today's globalized world, the social activity of young people is directly related to their outlook, way of thinking and, in general, their state of mind. The unstable and conflicting nature of the mind of young people definitely affects their behavior and activities. In our opinion, there are several reasons for this. First of all, the process of socialization of young people has become more complicated nowadays, so the factors of their social maturity have changed a lot. These factors are characterized not only by the fact that young people work independently, but also by finishing their education, having a profession, and becoming financially independent from adults. Second, the social maturity of young people is influenced by a number of independent factors (family, school, community, mass media, youth organizations and other groups). Each of these social mechanisms performs different tasks and has a different effect on youth education.

In fact, the social activity of young people means the general understanding of objective reality, the expression of its main social and psychological characteristics, and its implementation in practice. The personal attitude of young people to their internal capabilities for social activity is also important. It is at this time that young people develop the desire to evaluate themselves and others, to have personal views and perspectives. That is why it is important to always remember and take into account these aspects in education.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, we should focus on increasing the social initiative and activity of young people, increasing their professional training, forming their moral strength, encouraging them to obey the laws. In fact, the most important task of education should be to encourage young people to think independently about the problems of today, to plan the organization of personal activities in the new socio-economic system, and to implement these processes in harmony with universal human values. In fact, the youth is the backbone of the country, the trusted strength of the people, and the foundation of the nation's stability. That is why the content of the reforms implemented in our country is largely related to the fact that the owners of our future - young people - become mature and socially active in all aspects. In particular, the current era of globalization demands responsiveness and social activity from each growing young generation, and raises their spiritual and moral maturity to a more relevant level than ever before. In this sense, it is necessary to ensure the spiritual and moral basis of our every action in the activities carried out in the education of the young generation. In particular, the organization of social activity on the basis of moral norms and their non-discrimination by all people demonstrates democracy and social justice.

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